

USING ADVANTAGES OF TARGETED RESOURCES BY STATE FUNDING OF ENTERPRISES UNDER THE SOCIETY OF THE BLIND

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Abstract. *The given article deals with the use of targeted resources of state financing of production enterprises under the control of the society of the blind.*

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At present time the world economy is changing rapidly. It can be clearly considered as a result of the unification of the countries of the world into a single economic system, the economies of the countries are financially close to each other. Based on financial changes, we see that the economies of developing countries are developing in direct connection with the economies of developed countries.

In fact, economic ideas are always a product of their time and space. They are inextricably linked to this time and place, they cannot be considered independently, in isolation from the world they explain, and this world is constantly changing. This means that economic theories must also change if they are to serve their purpose.

It is not a secret that in the economies of developed countries, the issue of supporting the population in need of social protection and providing them with financial assistance from the state is legislatively regulated. It is the support of the state for the population in need of social protection, providing them with additional benefits that will provide practical assistance in ensuring employment for this category of people and realizing their potential.

Economics is an activity that provides people with material conditions and spiritual wealth. Resources, labor resources and needs, quality and quantitative characteristics of manufactured products are determined in advance, on the basis of which the social system is formed.

In recent years, the economy of Uzbekistan has also been developing in a form based on systemic market relations. In our country, the issue of supporting small businesses and entrepreneurship, ensuring employment of the population and establishing additional benefits for persons engaged in entrepreneurial activities is becoming relevant.

“Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, certainly, delusion.”

It is obvious that the constantly changing internal and external economic environment and its increasing influence on people, enterprises, countries and the whole world, be able to anticipate the actions and processes of economic activity that need to be carried out, in other words, economic activity. Insight is one of the qualities of a highly spiritual person, which cannot be imagined without deep economic knowledge and skills. Besides that, the science of “Economic Theory” occupies a leading place in educating people’s responsibility to society and the state, their economic responsibility regarding the organization of the economic life of society, active

participation in it and further development. We can build a democratic civil society based on free, socially oriented market economy that we are building by developing economic citizenship in all members of society.

In this regard, the presence of organizations operating on the basis of additional financial resources from the state requires a targeted allocation of financial resources from the state. All resources directly used in the production process are called factors of production. Regardless of the system and form of the economy, in order for production to take place, three factors must be present: labor, tools and objects of labor. It can be seen that factors of production, in contrast to economic resources, include only those resources that are directly involved in the process of production and service.

Certainly, a number of manufacturing enterprises operate under the management of the Society of the Blind of Uzbekistan. Many of us see that the working methods and technical equipment of these enterprises have been used for many years and that these technologies do not meet the requirements of today at all. Therefore, the government's allocation of additional financial resources to manufacturing enterprises under the control of the Uzbekistan Blind Society will help the operation of these enterprises in the future. For doing this it is necessary to allocate the following financial resources from the state.

1. Review of the material and technical base of enterprises of the blind society of Uzbekistan and assistance to them in creating financial and business programs.

2. Allocation of additional subsidies from the state to provide these enterprises with modern production technologies.

3. Creation of long-term strategic programs for the financial activities of enterprises of the Society of the Blind of Uzbekistan.

4. Provide government support in the sale of products produced by enterprises and participate in establishing mutual economic cooperation.

5. State support in establishing mutual cooperation with organizations of the blind in countries around the world.

Achieving financial sustainability of an enterprise managed by the Society of the Blind of Uzbekistan largely depends on international relations. That is, studying the conditions created for the blind in the leading countries of the world, establishing mutual experience when familiarizing themselves with the business plans of the enterprises where they work will help the development of organizations. In a society based on a market economy, if every manufacturer produces products that meet the requirements of the market, his purchasing power will undoubtedly increase. On the other hand, remaining with the old methods of production, the inability to enter into market relations does not allow production enterprises to operate financially. For this reason, it can be assured that the activities of these organizations will be good if any production is carried out openly, transparently, in accordance with market relations. In addition, if the industrial organizations under the control of the society of the blind use any financial resources allocated by the state, if they adapt their activities to the market economy and produce products that can be purchased, they will undoubtedly cope with their tasks and activities independently.

Definitely, entrepreneurship is one of the most important factors in a market economy. An entrepreneur is a person who ensures the integration of economic resources, that is, means of production and labor resources, natural resources, who is an organizer, strives for innovation, an initiator, who is not afraid of economic and other risks and responsibilities; the combination of

these qualities is called entrepreneurial ability. As the President of our country Sh. Mirziyoev suggested, “Active entrepreneurship is an economic direction that organizes business activities on the basis of innovative, that is, modern approaches, advanced technologies and management methods.” At present time in some sources, information and its means, ecology, are identified as a separate factor. In our opinion, they are expressed in the factors of nature and capital. Therefore, there is no need to consider them as a separate factor.

Factors of production never stand still in one place, but are constantly developing and growing. Both the means of production and labor are always in motion and development. This is proof of our idea to move from production based on a simple plow, hammer and ax to modern automated production. In order for the production process to take place, it is necessary to have a certain level of development of its infrastructure and its factors. Because many types of production and services cannot be carried out in an undeveloped place without this infrastructure. Therefore, they must develop in accordance with each other. Considering the role of production infrastructure in the development of the national economy, it requires a deeper understanding of its content as an economic category and its role in ensuring socio-economic development.

The concept of “infrastructure” comes from the Latin words “infra” - lower, under and “structure” - structure (that is, it can be interpreted in the sense of “substructure” or “additional”). At the beginning of the 20th century, this term meant a set of objects in the rear that ensure the movement of armed forces (warehouses, military bases, training grounds).

Since the mid-40s, this concept has entered applied economics, starting with Western economics. Due to this, a number of economic sectors serving industrial and agricultural production became clear.

From the above comments, we can conclude that production infrastructure is a collection of facilities serving the main production industry, creating and ensuring the general conditions necessary for the normal functioning of social production. It can be seen that the nature of the production infrastructure is manifested in the natural separation of entities providing auxiliary services to the main production, and organizations in the form of separate enterprises in the network. Industrial infrastructure enterprises occupy a secondary level in relation to the main production and in their development are always aimed at the needs of goods producers.

Production infrastructure is one of the direct and mandatory conditions for the functioning and development of the economic system, ensuring the unity of all phases of reproduction (production, distribution, exchange and consumption) in the economic system, its continuous functioning.

By summarizing it can be suggested that the stable operation of each manufacturing enterprise and the achievement of financial independence will directly depend on its production business plan, goals and activities for the coming years. Therefore, unless every manufacturer organizes its activities in a modern spirit, it will lag behind economically and will not be able to achieve its goals.

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